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Role

Industrial application

Pharmaceutical industry

Analgesic Antiviral Sedative Antineoplastic agent Antibiotic Cardiovascular drug Djuvar Emetic agent

Drug

Household products

Anti aids Emulsifier Personal care product

Surfactant Enzyme inhibitor

Food and nutrition

Indirect biological role

Metabolite

Neurotoxin

Immunotoxin

Mutagen

Biological role

Nutrient

Drug metabolite

Waste product

Energy storage

Gaba modulator

Energy source

Membrane stabilizer

Environmental role

Environmental contaminant